

WORKING ON PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE ACADEMIC LICEUMS OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14025679>

Abstract. *This article provides information about modern programs related to cybersecurity and safety.*

Keywords: *cybersecurity, Phishing, Cryptography, Encryption.*

INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of information technologies in all areas of society, including the activities of law enforcement agencies (LEAs), is yielding effective results in the implementation and improvement of modern methods for combating crime. The acceleration of information supply in LEA activities requires the regular collection of reliable data describing rapid situations and their timely and qualitative analysis, which are crucial factors in organizing the fight against crime. The automation of information processes relies on the implementation of computer technologies, the collection, storage, processing of data according to current requirements. Successfully addressing the problem of accelerating information supply in LEA activities requires training personnel with practical skills in the use of information technologies.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Currently, the attention given to information technologies and the subject of informatics and the numerous scientific research and investigations in this area contribute to the development of the discipline "Informatics and Information Technologies". For instance, M. Niyozov's dissertation titled "Improving the Teaching of Informatics and Information Technologies in Academic Lyceums Based on Web Technologies" thoroughly analyzes the structure, implementation stages, and methods of using web applications in teaching informatics in academic lyceums. [1] N. Otakhonov discusses modern methods of teaching subject-oriented programming languages in relation to issues of collecting, sorting, storing, processing, and transmitting professional activity-related information. [2] E. Migranova emphasizes the importance of fostering communication, organizational skills, and empathy among higher education students in organizing lessons on "Informatics and Information Technologies," which helps enhance lesson effectiveness. [3]

According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs were established in the regions in 2017. Currently, students at these lyceums acquire knowledge and skills in software, word processors, modern spreadsheet processors, presentation programs, computer viruses, programming languages, databases, graphic programs, computer networks, and web design, all in connection with school textbooks.

A personal computer consists of two organizational parts: hardware and software. Hardware refers primarily to the computer's main technical components and additional devices. Software, the second crucial part of a computer, comprises a set of programs that process data and

necessary documentation for operating the computer. All software can be classified into three categories:

- System software;
- Application software;
- Programming technology tools.

Microsoft Word is a versatile text editor used for creating, saving, modifying, formatting documents, and combining multiple documents into one. Electronic spreadsheets are primarily used for creating tables, solving economic problems, and performing calculations based on formulas, as well as creating graphics and diagrams. Microsoft PowerPoint is a presentation creation program that allows for the creation of modern presentations using 3D effects in slide design.

Working with databases is facilitated by special software. A collection of such software is referred to as database management systems (DBMS). Examples of DBMS include dBASE, Microsoft Access, and Microsoft Fox Pro for DOS. File compression and decompression are done using programs like WinRar and ZIP. To protect against viruses, various widely used antivirus programs are employed, such as Avast Free Antivirus, 360 Total Security, NOD32, Panda Dome, and DrWeb antivirus.

Modern programming languages include Delphi programming environment, its interface, and project creation and saving in Delphi. Concepts of modeling and simulation include stages of model creation, types of simulation, mathematical modeling, and graphical representation of simulation results.

Computer networks and their types involve network topologies, technical means of networks such as servers, concentrators, data transmission cables, and modems. Local area networks and the global computer network, including IP addresses on the Internet, domain names, resource (URL) addresses, protocols, and search engines, are also discussed. Email and its basic operations involve creating, sending, and reading messages.

Key concepts of information security include the issues surrounding it, major risks, and the organizational, legal, and technical methods for protecting information. Computer graphics and its types cover raster and vector graphics software, graphical tablets, working with ABBYY FineReader, and the Adobe Photoshop interface. Practical applications of software in professional fields include office applications, project management software, programs used in scientific research and calculations, multimedia software, engineering graphics software, and software used in economics and finance. Geographic information systems and their software are also relevant. The concepts of web pages, websites, and web design, along with their associated software and programs for creating and decorating web pages, such as Adobe Animate, are explored.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The changes and events occurring today in our country globally involve information circulating across all social networks. While these opportunities are positive, malicious individuals may exploit harmful software or gain users' trust to lead them to make mistakes. A single mistake can cost you valuable time and resources you have worked hard to acquire. The types of threats employed by cybercriminals also depend on the social media platforms being used. For instance, platforms like Facebook and Instagram guarantee the confidentiality of their users' personal information. Consequently, criminals typically aim to approach the friends of their

targeted victim online. If the aggressor can identify several friends of the targeted user, the likelihood of the victim accepting the friend request increases based on the number of mutual friends.

In the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, modern programs related to cybersecurity are taught to help students develop their professional skills. The implementation of training programs such as KALI LINUX and Kali Purple offers several advantages in the field of law enforcement:

- Revealing cybercrime.
- Providing technical support to computers.
- Working with network IP addresses.
- Recovering deleted files.
- Utilizing information protection software.

Cybersecurity is a set of measures aimed at protecting computer systems, networks, and data from cyberattacks and other threats. The importance of this field is related to several factors:

Protecting data: Cyberattacks can lead to the loss or theft of data, negatively affecting the activities of law enforcement agencies.

Ensuring security: Implementing cybersecurity within law enforcement enhances national security and protects citizens.

Training personnel: Preparing skilled professionals in the field of cybersecurity increases the effectiveness of the security system in our country.

Cybersecurity refers to measures taken to ensure the confidentiality of electronic information and protect against breaches or theft. It pertains to both software and hardware and applies to information on the Internet, encompassing everything from personal data to complex state systems, with several methods available to enhance the security of Wi-Fi networks. Phishing involves attempts to trick individuals into revealing personal information such as passwords, card numbers, or social security numbers. Cryptography, derived from Greek meaning "secret writing," studies the methods of encrypting open information and secret writing. It involves changing the text so that unauthorized individuals cannot understand it, using predefined symbols and methods for this purpose. There are various forms of this writing, including substituting letters with numbers, replacing letters with different conditional symbols, and altering letters in specified positions.

Integrating cybersecurity into the curriculum of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs holds significant importance in preparing young people for modern threats and equipping them with relevant skills. To effectively implement cybersecurity programs, it is necessary to improve resources, enhance teachers' qualifications, and introduce innovative approaches. Through these measures, students can be trained as successful professionals in the field of law enforcement.

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